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Abstract. The article examines the theoretical foundations of inclusive education and their application in the Kyrgyz context. It outlines behavioral, cognitive, and constructivist approaches, as well as disability models—medical, relational, and social—that inform policy and practice. International scholarship (Artiles, Florian, Treviranus, Kittay, and others) underscores the importance of equity, ethics of care, and digital technologies in fostering inclusion. In Kyrgyzstan, the legal framework includes the Law on the Rights and Guarantees of Persons with Disabilities (2008), the UN

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Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (ratified in 2019), and the State Program Accessible Country (2023–2030). However, practical implementation remains weak due to inadequate infrastructure, insufficient teacher training, and social stereotypes. National statistics reveal that 37.6 thousand children with disabilities live in the country, of whom about 20% remain outside the school system. International reports (Human Rights Watch, UN Special Rapporteur, UNICEF, EU initiatives) highlight systemic barriers such as inaccessible facilities, lack of assistive technologies, and insufficient interagency coordination. While international donors support reforms, inclusion in Kyrgyzstan is still largely declarative.

Introduction

Kyrgyzstan, like many other countries, faces the pressing challenge of the social integration of persons with disabilities (PWD). Despite legislative guarantees, young people with disabilities frequently encounter difficulties in accessing higher education and subsequent employment. Disability is a phenomenon that affects the lives of millions of people worldwide. According to estimates of the World Health Organization, 1.3 billion people (16% of the global population) live with significant disabilities, and this number continues to grow due to the increasing prevalence of chronic diseases and the overall aging of the population [WHO, 2025]. Persons with disabilities constitute a heterogeneous social group whose needs and life trajectories depend on a wide range of factors, including gender, age, cultural traditions, level of education, and socio-economic status. In Kyrgyzstan, the concept of disability is codified in normative legal acts [Government Decree No. 675 of December 14, 2016], which define the medical and social criteria for the recognition of disability. Despite legislative guarantees and measures adopted, including the ratification of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2019), the implementation of these norms remains weak due to insufficient funding, low public awareness, and the lack of adequate infrastructure for inclusive education.

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Main part. Inclusive education, as a scientific category, is grounded in various theoretical approaches that explain and guide the process of integrating persons with disabilities into the educational system. One of the fundamental directions is represented by learning theories—behaviorism, cognitivism, and constructivism. Their relationship to inclusive practices has been elaborated in the works of Al-Shammari, Faulkner, and Forlin, who demonstrated that inclusion requires teachers to combine methods of behavioral correction, cognitive development, and constructivist learning within a shared educational environment [Al-Shammari, Faulkner, & Forlin, 2019]. A significant contribution to the theoretical foundation has been made by studies on models of disability. Selisko and colleagues [Selisko et al., 2021] identify medical, relational, and social models, which are directly linked to types of inclusion (exclusion, functional inclusion, and full inclusion).

This framework helps to understand how different conceptual models shape educational policy. Equally important is the systemic perspective. Rapp [Rapp, 2021] applies social systems theory and constructionism to argue that inclusive education should be regarded as an institutional process dependent on the interaction of social norms, structures, and actors. The socio-ethical dimension of inclusive education is presented in Middleton's model [Middleton, 2019], which emphasizes six dimensions: learning and difference, social justice and human rights, humanism, praxis, creativity, and empowerment. Contemporary scholars also stress the need to incorporate intersectionality. Bešić [Beshich, 2020] highlights that effective inclusion must account not only for disability but also for its intersections with gender, age, ethnicity, and other social factors.

International scholars such as Artiles, Kozleski, and Waitoller [Artiles, Kozleski, & Waitoller, 2011] draw attention to issues of equity and educational justice, while Florian [Florian, 2014] advances the European concept of “learning for all.” The contributions of Jutta Treviranus lie in the development of inclusive design through the use of digital technologies [Treviranus, 2018], whereas Missy Morton investigates

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inclusive pedagogies and questions of assessment in education [Morton, 2012]. The philosophical foundation of inclusive education is further reinforced by the works of Eva Kittay, who examines it through the lens of the ethics of care and social justice [Kittay, 2011]. Thus, the theoretical basis of inclusive education is interdisciplinary in nature, bringing together pedagogical, social, philosophical, and technological approaches.

Inclusive education represents a strategy aimed at creating equal learning conditions for all categories of students. In international practice, it is regarded as an effective mechanism of social integration that enables persons with disabilities to participate in the educational process on an equal footing with others. The key principles of inclusion include: equal access to education; adaptation of curricula to individual needs; social integration and the development of tolerance; and comprehensive support provided by teachers, tutors, and specialists. In Kyrgyzstan, the legal framework for the implementation of inclusive education is defined by the Law on the Rights and Guarantees of Persons with Disabilities (2008), as well as by the State Program Accessible Country (2023–2030), which outlines measures to expand access of persons with disabilities to educational and employment resources. According to the National Statistical Committee, the number of persons with disabilities in Kyrgyzstan exceeds 200,000, which represents approximately 3% of the population. An analysis of trends between 2011 and 2023 demonstrates a 28.3% decrease in the number of individuals newly recognized as disabled (from 15,193 to 10,888), a decline that is largely attributed to improvements in diagnostics and the system of medical rehabilitation. However, the leading causes of disability remain diseases of the circulatory system (21.4%), malignant neoplasms (12.4%), and injuries (11.6%), which indicates the need to strengthen the prevention of non-communicable diseases and to improve social policy in the field of public health [National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2024]. In recent years, inclusive education in the Kyrgyz Republic has emerged as an important direction of state policy, yet its practical

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implementation remains limited. Official statistics indicate that there are 37.6 thousand children with disabilities under the age of 18, of whom approximately 79.3% are covered by formal education. At the same time, nearly 7.7 thousand children remain outside the school system due to the lack of accessible infrastructure, shortages of qualified personnel, and insufficient coordination between social and educational services [24.kg, 2025].

The formal acknowledgment of the necessity of inclusion is reflected in the new Law on Education (2023), which enshrines the principles of equal access and curriculum adaptation. Nevertheless, in practice only about 2,000 children are engaged in inclusive classrooms, representing a small proportion of the total [Kabar, 2025]. Experts emphasize that legislative norms remain largely declarative: the system of tutoring has not been established, individualized educational plans are not implemented, and the procedures of psycho-medical-pedagogical commissions frequently perpetuate segregation [Zhumabekova, 2023].

Studies conducted by international organizations also confirm the existence of serious challenges. According to Human Rights Watch, a significant proportion of schools remain physically inaccessible to children with disabilities due to the absence of ramps, elevators, and specialized sanitary facilities [Human Rights Watch, 2022]. The report of the United Nations Special Rapporteur on the rights of women and children (2025) further emphasizes that the main barriers are not limited to infrastructural deficiencies but also include inadequate teacher training, a lack of assistive technologies, and limited mechanisms for interagency coordination [UN, 2025]. Particular attention has been drawn to the quality of education. An analytical report by CABAR.asia highlights that although children with special educational needs are formally admitted to mainstream schools, there is no adaptation of teaching materials or systematic diagnostic support. As a result, such students often find themselves isolated within the educational environment, which negatively impacts both their academic performance and social development [CABAR.asia, 2022].

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At the same time, international donors and partners are actively supporting the development of an inclusive system. For instance, between 2021 and 2027, the European Union is implementing the Education Sector Reform program, with a total budget of €32 million, aimed at building a sustainable and inclusive education system that is ready to meet the challenges of the digital era [European Union, 2023]. UNICEF and Schools2030 have also stressed the need to reassess existing strategies and have recommended strengthening early diagnostics, teacher training, and the adoption of innovative teaching practices [UNICEF, 2023]. Thus, the current state of inclusive education for persons with disabilities in Kyrgyzstan is marked by a contradiction between the normative legal framework and the actual conditions of its implementation. Despite political will and international support, coverage remains limited, and institutional barriers hinder the full integration of children with disabilities into the educational environment. Achieving genuine inclusion requires not only the modernization of infrastructure and the training of qualified personnel but also a transformation of public consciousness aimed at recognizing the equal rights and opportunities of all citizens.

Despite legislative initiatives, a number of challenges persist in Kyrgyzstan: the limited material and technical capacity of educational institutions (absence of ramps, specialized learning materials, and adapted textbooks); insufficient training of teaching staff to work with children with disabilities; prevailing social stereotypes and discrimination; and weak coordination among state institutions, NGOs, and international organizations. These barriers result in inclusion remaining largely declarative. While children with special educational needs are admitted to mainstream schools, the absence of appropriate infrastructure and pedagogical support often leads to their isolation. Teachers generally lack sufficient knowledge of differentiated instruction methods, which makes it difficult to adapt curricula to the individual capacities of students. A particularly critical issue is the training of teaching staff. According to international monitoring data, fewer than 10% of teachers in Kyrgyzstan

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have completed specialized courses on inclusive education. This has resulted in the absence of a systemic approach: educators continue to operate within the framework of a traditional teaching model, where a child with a disability is perceived as a “deviation from the norm” rather than as an equal participant in the educational process. Equally important are entrenched social stereotypes. Within society, the notion remains widespread that children with disabilities should be educated in specialized boarding schools rather than in mainstream institutions. Such perceptions reinforce stigmatization and hinder the development of tolerance among peers, thereby limiting the opportunities of children with disabilities for genuine social integration. Moreover, weak interagency coordination prevents the establishment of comprehensive support for students with disabilities and their families. Government bodies, non-governmental organizations, and international donors often act in a fragmented manner, which leads to the duplication of programs, inefficient use of resources, and the absence of sustainable outcomes. Therefore, for the effective development of inclusive education, it is necessary not only to update the regulatory framework but also to ensure its practical implementation through the creation of barrier-free infrastructure, the development of a tutoring system, the regular training of teachers, and the transformation of public attitudes. Only through a comprehensive approach can inclusive education move beyond declarative statements and become a truly functioning system that guarantees equal opportunities for all children.

The prospects for the development of inclusive education in Kyrgyzstan are directly linked to the fulfillment of international commitments and the adoption of successful practices from other countries. The ratification of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2019) obliges the state not only to make declarative statements but also to take concrete steps toward ensuring equal access to education for all categories of citizens. First, a key priority is the creation of barrier-free infrastructure. In Finland and Canada, public investment is directed toward ensuring that every school meets physical accessibility standards, including the

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provision of ramps, elevators, adapted sanitary facilities, specialized learning materials, and digital resources. Kyrgyzstan needs to adopt similar standards, which would eliminate physical barriers and increase the participation of children with disabilities in mainstream education. Second, the preparation of teaching staff is of crucial importance. In EU countries such as Germany and the Netherlands, training in inclusive methodologies is a mandatory component of teacher education programs. In Kyrgyzstan, however, only a small number of teachers have completed specialized courses, which reduces the effectiveness of inclusion efforts. To address this gap, a systemic professional development program is required, one that incorporates modern methods of differentiated and multimodal learning, as well as the development of a formal tutoring system. Third, it is essential to foster interagency and cross-sectoral cooperation. In Kazakhstan, where national strategies for inclusive education are being implemented, coordination among the ministries of education, health, and labor has been established. This approach enables comprehensive support for children and their families—from early diagnosis to vocational guidance. The introduction of a similar model in Kyrgyzstan would enhance the efficiency of resource utilization and eliminate the duplication of functions among government agencies and NGOs.

In addition, a promising direction is the digitalization of the educational environment. The use of online platforms, electronic textbooks, and assistive technologies (such as screen readers, software for the visually impaired, and educational applications) creates new opportunities for the individualization of learning. International experience demonstrates that technology significantly reduces barriers and allows children with disabilities to participate in the educational process on an equal footing with their peers. Finally, particular attention must be paid to the formation of an inclusive culture within society. The experience of Canada and the Scandinavian countries demonstrates that the sustainable implementation of inclusive education is possible only through a transformation of public consciousness. In Kyrgyzstan, awareness-raising campaigns are needed to combat stereotypes and

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discrimination, to foster tolerance among children and parents, and to promote a positive image of persons with disabilities as equal members of society. Thus, the prospects for inclusive education in Kyrgyzstan lie in the comprehensive modernization of the system: from infrastructural improvements and teacher training to digitalization and the transformation of public perceptions. Only the integration of international practices, adapted to the national context, will make it possible to create a sustainable and effective model that ensures equal educational opportunities for all children.

Conclusion

Inclusive education in the Kyrgyz Republic is gradually becoming an integral part of national educational policy and the country's international commitments. The ratification of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, the adoption of the new Law on Education (2023), and participation in international programs supported by the EU and UNICEF all testify to the state's intention to create conditions for equal access to education for all children. However, an analysis of the current situation reveals that the normative and legal framework is not yet supported by sufficient resources and systemic measures.

The majority of children with disabilities continue to face physical barriers, a lack of adapted learning materials, insufficiently trained teachers, and weak interagency coordination. Social stereotypes and discriminatory practices further limit their opportunities for integration into the educational environment.

The prospects for the development of inclusion in Kyrgyzstan largely depend on political will and the state's ability to implement comprehensive reforms. Substantial investments in barrier-free infrastructure, systematic teacher and tutor training, the digitalization of educational processes, and awareness-raising campaigns aimed at fostering an inclusive culture in society are all required. The experience of European

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and North American countries demonstrates that sustainable change is only possible when legislative guarantees are combined with professional training and broad public support.

Thus, inclusive education in Kyrgyzstan remains at the formative stage. It represents not only an educational but also a social challenge, directly linked to the level of democratization, social justice, and humanization of society.

The implementation of inclusive principles will be a crucial step toward building a society in which every citizen, regardless of health status, can realize their potential and contribute to the overall development of the country.

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